

EXCELERATE Deliverable 2.2

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1. Table of contents

Table of contents	2
Executive Summary	2
Impact	3
Project objectives	4
Delivery and schedule	5
Adjustments made	5
Background information	5
Appendix 1: A report on the structure of the openEBench platform and its coordination with WP1 on the incorporation of monitoring statistics and benchmarking results in registry releases, and other ELIXIR platforms	9
8.1. OpenEBench. The ELIXIR benchmarking platform	9
8.2. Metrics for Tools monitoring	12
8.3. Exporting data from OpenEBench	18
8.3.1. OpenEBench Website	19
8.3.2. RESTful API's	22
8.3.3. Widgets	23
8.4. Coordination with other ELIXIR activities.	25
8.5. Future developments	26
8.6. Relevant URLs related to OpenEBench	27

2. Executive Summary

The objective of Deliverable 2.2 is to report the integration of benchmarking activities in the ELIXIR Tools Platform ecosystem. During the execution of the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE project the original tasks of WP2 have evolved to the generation of a integrated platform, OpenEBench, that supersedes the scope of initial Task 2.3 (section 5). For this reason, this first deliverable after the availability of the release of OpenEBench, presented in ELIXIR All Hands meeting, June 2018, contains also a detailed presentation of the management of Tools Monitoring metrics in the platform. Rationale and motivations about OpenEBench as ELIXIR integrated platform is described in section 8.1. OpenEBench aims to become a central hub for information about tools performance, covering three main aspects: i) scientific performance, ii) software quality, and iii) technical performance. Scientific performance is largely based in the work of scientific communities. OpenEBench provides a central data warehouse where such communities can expose their benchmarking activities for experts and non-experts users covering software developers, community participants, researchers, and/or funding bodies. The data model

supporting OpenEBench efforts was outlined in a previous deliverable ([D2.1: Creation of a database warehouse infrastructure for storing and organizing data for online performance assessment experiments](#)) and will not be described here. Future developments of OpenEBench will focus in the generation of an automated platform for supporting scientific benchmarking activities driven by communities. This development will be largely related to the evolution of the ELIXIR platform for software deployment (Biocontainers), and the deployment for solutions for workflow specification and execution from ELIXIR's interoperability and compute platforms. Tools monitoring activity in OpenEBench is the central issue in D2.2. We describe the series of metrics that are being currently implemented (Section 8.2), and show how data can be obtained from the platform (Section 8.3). OpenEBench have developed a comprehensive web portal (<https://openebench.bsc.es>), the main access point to the platform for end-users. Also, data is accessible via a series of RESTful APIs for programmatic consumption. This is particularly relevant since this the main way other ELIXIR platforms like the Tools Registry bio.tools will access benchmarking data. Finally, a series of HTML widgets, ready to be embedded into other platforms portals are made available. OpenEBench was released in the occasion of ELIXIR All Hands 2018 Conference in Berlin, but it is still in constant evolution (see section 8.6).

The original aim of D2.2 was to document the relationships with ELIXIR-EXCELERATE WP1, in particular the bio.tools registry. This close relationship has indeed happened, and now bio.tools shows OpenEBench widget in its tool cards, and all tools registered in bio.tools are being monitored in OpenEBench, the information completed with data from other sources, and made available for reuse by bio.tools. However, the scope has now been extended (section 8.5) to a general engagement of benchmarking activities with other ELIXIR platforms and activities. In particular, we gather data from other software related activities, in particular from Biocontainers/Bioconda and Galaxy initiatives. We collect and expose information following the bioschemas standards promoted by the ELIXIR Interoperability platform, and we are in close contact with the compute platform to build the benchmarking execution services according to their standards. Following the ELIXIR Software development best-practice group, OpenEBench is a fully open source project (Section 8.7) from day 1 with an ecosystem of publicly available repositories for the different platform components¹.

3. Impact

We have engaged to different degrees with the following scientific communities.

- CAMEO. Continuous Automated Model EvaluatiOn.
- QfO. Quest for Orthologs.
- GMI. Global Microbial Identification Initiative - Benchmarking Group.
- CAID. Continuous Assessment of Intrinsic protein Disorder.
- Driver Cancer Genes Group. The Cancer Genome Atlas.
- CAMI. Critical Assessment of Metagenome Interpretation.
- CoCoBench. Community-based Continuous Benchmarking for Core Facilities.

¹ Jiménez RC, Kuzak M, Alhamdoosh M et al. Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software, F1000Research 2017, 6:876 (doi:[10.12688/f1000research.11407.1](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11407.1)).

We have also organized a number of internal and external workshops around the scientific benchmarking efforts including the [WS6: Benchmarking Incentives and Best Practices Across Scientific Disciplines – Abstracting from Established Evaluations](#) held during the [BC]² Conference in Basel in September, 2017, with more than 30 participants. Other [relevant workshops](#) have been held during the [ELIXIR Tools Platform meeting in Barcelona, February 2018](#); and the [ELIXIR All Hands Meeting in Berlin, June 2018](#), with more than 20 registered attendees each.

OpenEBench currently monitors technical aspects of 15,002 bioinformatics tools, servers and workflows. Moreover, it exposes that information via available APIs to other platforms like the ELIXIR Tools Registry bio.tools and the Galaxy Shed.

4. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Systematically organize the relations to communities already running benchmarking exercises within biology and medicine. (Task 2.1)		X
2	Development and maintenance of a generic infrastructure to support benchmarking exercises in different subareas. (Task 2.2)	X	
3	Develop the technology to perform online, uninterrupted methods assessment in key areas of bioinformatics. (Task 2.3)		X
4	Development and implementation of data warehouse infrastructures to store benchmarking results and to make them accessible to benchmark participants and method developers for subsequent transfer to the ELIXIR registry. (Task 2.4)	X	
5	Development of the procedures to create standards in the different fields subject to benchmarking. (Task 2.5)	X	
6	Establish workshops, hackathons and jamborees for different user communities. (Task 2.6)		X

5. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

6. Adjustments made

The scope of the deliverable have been extended to present a throughout overview the initial release of the OpenEBench platform. Also, relationships with WP1 will be complemented with the relationships with other ELIXIR platforms.

7. Background information

Background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	2	Start date or starting event:	month 1
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Work package title	Benchmarking
Lead	Alfonso Valencia (BSC) and Søren Brunak (DTU)
Participant number and person months per participant 7 – CNIO 2.00; 8 - CRG 20.6; 10 - IRB 12; 12 - BSC 28; 25 - SIB 23; 38 - DTU 6. <i>CNIO and BSC activities are reported together since CNIO partners moved to BSC within the Grant Agreement 2nd Amendment.</i>	
Objectives The concept of assessing bioinformatics methods in terms of quantitative performance and user friendliness is crucial to the development of the infrastructure in the general field of bioinformatics. Accordingly, WP2 will focus on the following objectives: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Systematically organize the relations to communities already running benchmarking exercises within biology and medicine. (Task 2.1)2. Development and maintenance of a generic infrastructure to support benchmarking exercises in different subareas. (Task 2.2)3. Develop the technology to perform online, uninterrupted methods assessment in key areas of bioinformatics. (Task 2.3)4. Development and implementation of data warehouse infrastructures to store benchmarking results and to make them accessible to benchmark participants and method developers for subsequent transfer to the ELIXIR registry. (Task 2.4)5. Development of the procedures to create standards in the different fields subject to benchmarking. (Task 2.5)6. Establish workshops, hackathons and jamborees for different user communities. (Task 2.6)	
Work Package Leads: Alfonso Valencia (ES) and Søren Brunak (DK)	
Description of work and role of partners WP2 - Benchmarking [Months: 1-48] BSC, CNIO, CRG, IRB, SIB, DTU World-wide, bioinformaticians already engage significantly with evaluation exercises in the form of open challenges.	

The role model for this type of effort is the still on-going "Critical Assessment of protein Structure Prediction, or CASP, which is a community-wide, world-wide experiment for protein structure prediction taking place every two years since 1994. This effort, as well as others, provide research groups with an opportunity to objectively test their prediction methods and delivers an independent assessment of the state of the art to the research community and software users.

CASP has inspired many other similar experiments, including analysis of text mining methods (BioCreative), docking (Capri): force-field evaluation for atomistic simulations and benchmarking of small molecule docking, evaluation of multiple alignments, NGS sequencing variation analysis, gene finding and others. All these community efforts have a similar organization and similar basic infrastructure needs. A further challenge is to make these challenges not only static annual or bi-annual competitions, but to evaluate the systems in an online fashion, which would make them more sustainable. A few experiments were organized in the past (e.g. the EVA effort organized by Burkhard Rost and co-workers), but abandoned for technical reasons. In a close collaboration with the Continuous Automated Model Evaluation (CAMEO) platform, which is running continuously since 2012, the WP will build on these concepts such that methods can be benchmarked based on data, which are novel to all, including the methods developers in more sustainable frameworks.

It is an essential part of the European infrastructure since:

- It provides a strong connection between the ELIXIR infrastructure and the communities carrying out benchmarking exercises within their expert knowledge domains.
- It is directly linked to the information to be disseminated in the ELIXIR tools and services registry.
- Provides direct access to information on methods and performance measures for end-users.
- Provides the benchmarking data needed for training of new methods making progress in the different subareas of field.
- Furthermore, the benchmarking activities will provide a great vehicle for developing novel standards for data and methods thus also providing useful input to other WPs.

Task 2.1: Organize the relations with communities already running benchmarking exercises (7.6PM).

Obtain agreement with existing communities on the conditions of challenges, organizes, formats, goals and other organizational issues that can lead to harmonization of efforts world-wide in addition to division of labour decisions.

Partners: ES, DK

Task 2.2: Development and maintenance of a generic infrastructure to support benchmarking in different areas (12PM).

The emerging ELIXIR registry will be a reference for the research community. The methods to be benchmarked will be described in the registry with the proper version control and automatic access procedures. At the same time a generic infrastructure is needed in order to organize data for new and existing benchmarking efforts. WP2 will be responsible of implementing the guidelines and standards for data organization and submission of the different methods subsequently to be incorporated in the registry. We will also collect qualitative and quantitative data about the usage of these services, and different indicators about the service itself (i.e. data grow rate, uptime, etc.). These data will be stored in the data warehouse infrastructure (Task 2.4). Opinion leaders in the field will be surveyed about how useful they consider the resources are and the results will be included in the registry.

Partners: ES, DK

Task 2.3: Develop the technology to perform online, uninterrupted methods assessment in key areas of bioinformatics (18PM).

In order to make online methods performance assessment several infrastructure elements need to be in place in order to support the various challenges. These include:

- Organization of a collection of training data (validated by experts),
- Identification, collection and organization of a collection of testing data which are kept secret,
- Community agreements on the data standards, submission formats and evaluation methods (quality assessment),
- Hosting or accessing methods (e.g. by programmatic access) to obtain results from them automatically without human intervention,
- Parsing, organization and display of the results with proper statistics and comparison facilities.

Partners: ES, DK, CH

Task 2.4: Development and implementation of data warehouse infrastructures to store benchmarking results and to make them accessible to users and method developers (18PM).

In this task we will develop with the each one of the communities the necessary data framework and method standards, based on the community recommendations and the experience acquired in each challenge. The standards will be essential for the operation of the benchmarking infrastructure. The standards will also facilitate the end- users interpretation of the results, and we will develop tools for the conversion of the data from different formats into the most frequent standards in collaboration with WP1. We will also develop tools to diagnose and rate the ELIXIR resources according to the level of agreement with those standards.

Partners: ES, DK, CH

Task 2.5: Development of the procedures to create standards in the different fields subject to benchmarking (7PM).

Data warehouses are key to storing and analysing the very large collection of data that will be generated by the prediction methods. Part of the WP2's mission is to store these data in a way such that they can be used for the continuous evaluation of the methods and for training of new methods. With time the ambition is that this infrastructure will be the main infrastructure of the different communities in subareas from protein structure and feature prediction to genomics and cheminformatics.

Partners: ES, DK

Task 2.6: Establish workshops and jamborees for the different user communities (7PM).

The final goal of the infrastructure is to provide users with a continuous evaluation of bioinformatics methods and to have a positive influence on tools development. The effort requires a robust system for the provision of testing data, running methods and evaluating results. The design of the most adequate representation system for each of the areas will require additional software development efforts. In the training workshops and jamborees representatives of the scientific communities involved in the project will participate alongside new communities interested in adapting their challenges to the use of the infrastructure. The training aspects will be coordinated with the other training efforts in the project.

Partners: ES, DK

8. Appendix 1: A report on the structure of the openEBench platform and its coordination with WP1 on the incorporation of monitoring statistics and benchmarking results in registry releases, and other ELIXIR platforms

8.1. OpenEBench. The ELIXIR benchmarking platform

The dependence of the scientific advance on research software is increasing in all science fields, but notably in biology where the availability of growing amounts of data coming from large scale genomics projects has put an extra concern in the possibility of properly analyzing such data, and hence assure the outcomes of such projects. Bioinformatics as a science has become a need at all levels of biology. It is no longer a private space where some specialized researchers develop and test new methodologies for the sake of their own scientific objectives. Bioinformatics methods

and tools have now to be consumed by the whole of the biological community. This puts an extra challenge in the development of research software². Bioinformaticians should prepare software for the use of non experts, and have to compete in a continuously evolving market of alternative options, proving with objective metrics that the software is usable, efficient, and gives the adequate answers. Benchmarking has been a traditional activity in bioinformatics, although it has been mostly conducted by scientific communities, for internal consumption and seldom considered by final users of the software³.

In this context, the need for an open platform around benchmarking has become evident. **OpenEBench**⁴, the main outcome of ELIXIR-EXCELERATE WP2 seeks to fill this gap and the three levels of benchmarking: i) scientific benchmarking related to the scientific quality of bioinformatics tools; ii) technical monitoring related to software quality; and iii) performance benchmarking regarding the usability and efficiency of the technical deployment of bioinformatics tools, servers and/or workflows. Overall, OpenEBench should provide information for i) end-users, deciding which resource is the most appropriate for their problem at hand, ii) software developers, seeking for accepted best practices in research software, and testing their own tools against the accepted and/or possibly competing alternatives, iii) infrastructure providers, seeking to design an adequate provision of tools, servers and/or workflows, and iv) funders, requiring an overview of a given field, and checking the outcome of funded activities. A number of other initiatives do exist within and outside ELIXIR that clearly intersects of OpenEBench aims. In particular, tool's registries, mainly bio.tools registry⁵ (from ELIXIR-EXCELERATE WP1), aggregated tools libraries like BioConda⁶ or Galaxy tool-shed⁷, or software deployment platforms like BioContainers⁸. OpenEBench is designed as an information Hub (Figure 1), where data will be collected from those sources, and others, processed, and redistributed back for the use of those platforms and also to the already mentioned group of users.

² Silva LB, Jimenez RC, Blomberg N and Luis Oliveira J. General guidelines for biomedical software development *F1000Research* 2017, **6**:273. ([doi:10.12688/f1000research.10750.2](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.10750.2))

³ Capella-Gutiérrez S, De la Iglesia D, Haas J. et al. Lessons Learned: Recommendations for Establishing Critical Periodic Scientific Benchmarking bioRxiv 181677 (doi.org/10.1101/181677)

⁴ <https://openebench.bsc.es>

⁵ <https://bio.tools>

⁶ <https://bioconda.github.io/>

⁷ <https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/>

⁸ <http://biocontainers.pro/>

Figure 1. OpenEBench philosophy as information hub.

The roadmap for OpenEBench development has been organized as follows:

1. Design and development of a comprehensive data model to hold benchmarking data (Task 2.4, Completed, BSC, SIB)
2. Select a series of scientific communities active and mature in benchmarking activities, and incorporate a digested summary of their already available benchmarking data into OpenEBench repository (Task 2.1, Completed, BSC, SIB, CRG, IRB)
3. Experiment and develop visualization alternatives to offer a quick overview of scientific benchmarking data suitable to be incorporated to software registries (T2.2, ongoing, BSC, SIB)
4. Define an extensive list of software quality metrics, and develop the necessary interfaces for gathering such information (completed, Section 8.2, BSC, DTU)
5. Develop a simple visual element (HTML widget) to summarize software quality data that can be exported to registries like bio.tools (available in bio.tools, section 8.3, BSC, DTU)
6. Develop the necessary API's to distribute benchmarking data to the community and to ELIXIR information ecosystem (ongoing, section 8.3, BSC, SIB, CRG).
7. Develop an automated platform to apply benchmarking metrics, that can evolve to host complete scientific benchmarking events (Task 2.3, prototype for benchmarking metrics, BSC, CRG).
8. Develop an automated platform to evaluate technical and scientific performance of bioinformatics tools under the same technical environment (Task 2.3, BSC).

The present document focuses in reporting the achievements regarding the establishment of the data repository (Step 1), the building of the Tools monitoring infrastructure (Steps 4, 6), the

development of visualization models (Steps 3, 5), and their connection with other ELIXIR components, as bio.tools.

8.2. Metrics for Tools monitoring

Software quality is a key issue in research⁹, as the quality of scientific outcomes is clearly ligated to the quality of the tools used to deliver them. Bioinformatics as a whole has been largely accused of generating poor research software due to the prioritization of the quick results over the optimization and standardization of the tools used. This is not unexpected, as bioinformatics is a fast evolving field. Accepted algorithms become obsolete far before the software made out of them can reach the usual quality standards normal in other disciplines. While this is traditionally accepted as normal use by researchers, it puts strong questions in the reproducibility of research results and on the validity of processed data deposited in large archives like, for instance, the European Genome-Phenome archive¹⁰. In this latter case a pilot study about re-analyzing datasets is undergoing within the European Science Cloud pilots initiative¹¹.

OpenEBench, as indicated above, holds a specific infrastructure to monitor software quality. In an initial analysis phase BSC has put together a series of quality metrics taken from a number of sources. The source of such metrics includes documents by the Software Sustainability Institute¹², recommendations for open source software development¹³, or for software quality metrics⁹. For each metric, a specific source of information have been chosen and the necessary interface implemented. Table 1 collects the actual metrics being monitored in the present version of OpenEBench.

Table 1. Tools monitoring metrics.

C: General Information. V: Information per version

Data Sources: Reg: Software registries (e.g. bio.tools), Repo: Software repositories (e.g. GitHub); Web: Text mining on available URLs; Publ: Text mining on publications

Metric Name	Description	Values	Data Source
Tools Id/s			
Resource ID	Main Id (primary key). It should correspond to	Required	Reg

⁹ Artaza H, Chue Hong N, Corpas M *et al.* Top 10 metrics for life science software good practices. *F1000Research* 2016, 5(ELIXIR):2000. (doi: [10.12688/f1000research.9206.1](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.9206.1))

¹⁰ <https://ega-archive.org/>

¹¹ <http://eoscipilot.eu/>

¹² <https://www.software.ac.uk/software-evaluation-guide>

¹³ Jiménez RC, Kuzak M, Alhamdoosh M *et al.* Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software, *F1000Research* 2017, 6:876 (doi:[10.12688/f1000research.11407.1](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11407.1)).

	one of the known IDs prefixed		
Alternative ID/s	List of prefix:ids. Prefix should reflect data repository	Optional	Reg, Repo
Resource version/s	List of prefix:IDs:version	Optional	Reg, Repo
Resource deployment/s	Multiple deployments for the same tool ID:version	Required	Reg, Repo
Usability:Understability			
Description (C)	Whether high-level description of the tool is available. It should contain concept, rationale and application . By application we understand what the software is for.	Text	Reg, Repo, Web, Publ
Architecture (C)	Whether architectural overview, with diagrams, is available.	Yes / No	Repo, Web, Publ
Use-case (C)	Whether case studies of use are available. Example of use.	Yes / No	Repo, Web, Publ
Usability:Documentation			
Help (V)	Whether there is a general help about how to use the tool	Yes (link/s) / No	Repo, Web, Publ
Tutorial (V)	Whether there is a tutorial associated	Yes (link/s) / No	Repo, Web, Publ
README/How To (V)	Whether there is a readme file distributed along the code.	Yes (link/s) / No	Repo, Web, Publ
Publication/s (V)	Whether the resource has an associated publication	Yes (link/s) / No	Repo, Web
How to Cite (V)	Whether the resource includes an statement on how to cite it and potentially associated algorithms, methods, etc	Yes / No	Repo, Web
APIs (V)	Complete API documentation (e.g. JavaDoc, Doxygen).	Yes (link/s) / No	Reg, Repo
Repositories (V)	Whether the API documentation is held under version control system.	Yes (link/s) / No	Reg, Web, Publ
Source/comments ratio (V)	Ratio code/comments, code lines/document lines. It reflects how much the code is documented.	Computed ratio	Repo.

Identity & Findability			
Website (C)	Project/software has a web page.	Yes (link/s) / No	Reg, Publ
Domain (C)	Project/software has its own domain name.	Yes / No	Reg, Publ
Trademark (C)	Project/software name is a trademark.	Yes / No	Reg, Web, Publ
Robots compatible (V)	Could Search Engine Robots track their website?	Yes / No	Web
Registries (V)	Software registries that include the software	Yes (link/s) / No	Reg
Scientific benchmark availability (V)	Software is a part of scientific benchmark activities	Yes (link/s) / No	Reg, Web, Publ OpenEBench Sci.
Recognizability (C)	Project/software has a distinct name within its application area.	Computed Yes / No	Web, Publ
Bioschemas markup (C)	Whether the Web site include markup following bioschemas	Yes/No	Web
Usability:Buildability & Installability			
Build instructions (V)	Whether instructions for building the software are provided	Yes / No	Repo, Web
Installation instructions (V)	Whether instructions for installing the software are provided	Yes / No	Repo, Web
Build dependencies (V)	Whether the list of all third-party dependencies for proper project build is provided.	Yes (link/s) / No	Repo, Web
Execution dependencies (V)	Whether the list of all third-party runtime dependencies is provided.	Yes (link/s) / No	Repo, Web
Execution test (V)	Whether the software has specific tests to ensure the correct installation	Yes / No	Repo
Virtual environments (V)	Whether the resource could be built into a virtual environment such as BioConda	Yes (value) / No	Repo, Web, Publ
Type (V)	Type of the automated build system used (make, maven, ant, etc).	Yes (value) / No	Repo, Web

Package-based installation (V)	Whether the software can be installed from pre-configured packages e.g. RPMs, DEBs, PiP, CPAN, PECL	Yes (value) / No	Repo, Web, Publ
Language (V)	Code source language. Whether it is compiled (C, C++, C#) or interpreted (Python, Perl, Ruby)	Yes (value) / No	Reg, Repo
Operative system (V)	Operative system used to build the software (Unix or Not)	Unix (Yes / No)	Reg, Repo
Compiler warnings	Whether the compiler gives warnings. Compilation success	computed ratio	Repo
Copyright			
Copyright statement	Website states copyright.	Yes / No	Reg, Repo, Web, Publ
Credits	Web site states who developed/develops the software, funders etc.	Yes / No	Reg, Repo, Web, Pub
Consistency	All sites state exactly the same copyright, licencing and authorship.	Yes / No	Reg, Repo, Web, Pub
Copyright headers	Each source code file has a copyright statement.	Yes / No	Repo
Licensing			
Project license	Project has a license	Yes / No	Reg, Repo, Web, Pub
License statement	Website states license.	Yes / No	Web
Source code license	Code distribution includes a license file.	Yes / No	Repo
License headers	Each source code file has a license header.	Yes / No	Repo
Open source	Project has an open source license.	Yes / No	Reg, Repo, Web, Pub
OSI	Software has an Open Software Initiative (OSI)-recognised license.	Yes / No	Reg, Repo, Web, Pub
Accessibility			
Binary distribution	Whether binary distributions are available.	Yes / No	Repo, Web

Binary distribution freeness	Binary distributions are freely available.	Yes / No	Repo, Web
Binaries download registration	Binary distributions are available without the need for any registration.	Yes / No	Repo, Web
Source code	Source distributions are available.	Yes / No	Repo, Web
Source code freeness	Source distributions are freely available.	Yes / No	Repo, Web
Source code download registration	Source code is available without the need for any registration.	Yes / No	Repo, Web
Source code repository	Access to source code repository is available.	Yes / No	Repo
Source code anonymous access	Anonymous read-only access to source code repository.	Yes / No	Repo, Web
Source code repository browse	Ability to browse source code repository online.	Yes / No	Repo
Source code repository accessible	Make sure the repository (github, bit bucket) contains code	Yes / No	Repo
Source code repository version controlled	Check whether code contains any information about versions/releases/tags	Yes / No	Repo
Supportability & User Support			
e-mail	Project has an e-mail address.	Yes / No	Reg, Repo, Web, Publ
Changeability			
Contributions policy	Whether the project has defined a contributions policy.	Text	Repo
Issue tracker	Whether the tool has a publicly accessible issue tracker.	Yes / No	Repo
Resolve time	How long are issues open.	duration	Repo
Governance	Whether the project has defined a governance model.	Text	Repo, Web

OpenEBench implements the series of metrics detailed on Table 1 feeding from a number of providers. The main source of information corresponds to ELIXIR-EXCELERATE WP1's bio.tools

registry⁵, but primary data is also collected from BioConda repository⁶ and Galaxy Tool-Shed⁷. Additionally, OpenEBench uses information available, mainly publications and URLs to perform additional analyses from publications archives like Europe PMC¹⁴, NCBI PubMed¹⁵, and WikiData¹⁶. Software repositories API's (mainly GitHub¹⁷) is the source for buildability metrics, software dependencies, available releases and project contributors Websites (from the available URLs) are parsed for BioSchemas markup¹⁸, and also analyzed using text-mining strategies to derive additional information, in particular regarding documentation. In addition to the retrieval of static data from the repositories or associated documentation, URLs are actively tested in a daily basis in terms of availability and response time. This is, naturally, of prime importance, in the case of on-line tools, although also software repositories are checked for changes in their availability.

The OpenEBench repository aims to offer the users with clear view of the usability of the tools under study. It complements the information available in other registries, by keeping record of the different deployment options (Command line, software packages, Galaxy instances, web portal), and also of the versions of the software available in real time.

The present contents of OpenEBench Tools monitoring repository contains 15,002 tools corresponding to over 22,000 deployments, all of them actively checked. Other metrics are less encouraging, although almost all show a clear description of the tools: only 2,800 (19%) have an easily accessible documentation other than a simple description; 3,300 (23%) an open source licence or a terms of use document. Table 2 shows a summary of the analytic metrics at the time of writing.

Table 2. Summary of quality metrics at OpenEBench repository.

Metrics Name	Total	Percentage %
Tools Id/s		
Resource ID	15,002	100%
Documentation		
Description	14,850	99%
Help	670	5%
Manual	2,322	15%
Tutorial	222	2%

¹⁴ <https://europepmc.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/>

¹⁶ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

¹⁷ <https://github.com/>

¹⁸ <http://bioschemas.org/>

Publications	11,107	74%
Identity & Findability		
Website	15,002	100%
bioschemas	455	3%
Buildability & Installability		
Language	5,232	35%
Operating system	5,758	38%
Copyright		
Copyright statement	479	3%
Credits	2,089	14%
Licensing		
Project license	5,411	36%
Open source	2,801	19%
OSI	2,724	18%
Accessibility		
Binary distribution	4,346	29%
Source code	4,639	30%
Source code repositories	586	4%
Supportability & User Support		
e-mail	8,138	54%
Changeability		
Issues tracker	17	<1%

8.3. Exporting data from OpenEBench

As indicated, a distinct aim of the OpenEBench platform is to disseminate the available information for consumption of end-users directly or through other ELIXIR platforms. To this end a number of options have been put in place.

8.3.1. OpenEBench Website

End-users are expected to arrive to OpenEBench from links available at other ELIXIR resources, mainly the tools registry bio.tools, although we provide a complete web site to include both information on scientific benchmarking and tools monitoring. OpenEBench website is available at <https://openebench.bsc.es>, where the two main sections (Scientific Benchmarking and Tools Monitoring) can be accessed (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Landing page of OpenEBench main website.

The tools monitoring section allows to perform a complete search (Figure 3), including tools titles and description, and relevant annotations like EDAM's operation and topic terms¹⁹.

¹⁹ <http://edamontology.org>

Figure 3. Screenshot of OpenEBench Tools monitoring search results.

The selection of a given tool gives access to the specific card (Figure 4) where general information of the tools, their possible implementations and links to the sources of information are available.

Metrics	
Accessibility:	Source code YES
Licensing:	OSI YES Open source YES
Documentation:	General NO FAQ NO Manual NO
Support:	Email YES

Figure 4. Example of Tool's card. Example entry: pmut

In addition to the general metrics Indicated in Table 1, OpenEBench Tool Card includes life information about the availability of the tool, as obtained from monitoring the relevant URLs. This check is done in a daily basis and includes, up/down state, time of response, and for encrypted (https) links the validity of the encryption setup. Figure 5 shows an example of such information.

Figure 5. Monitoring tools availability and response time. Example entry: trimal.

Finally, an updated record of the citations received by the publications associated to the tool is provided (Figure 6). The procedure to obtain the list of citations is the next:

1. Fetch from OpenEBench the list of tools with bibliographic references (i.e. PubMed Ids, DOIs and/or PMC ids).
2. For each one of these bibliographic references, query several bibliographic sources for records about them. We are currently using Europe PMC¹⁴, NCBI PubMed¹⁵ and WikiData¹⁶, through their programmatic APIs, as bibliographic and citation providers. For each source, a correspondence from each bibliographic identifier and its internal id is obtained.
3. For those matched identifiers, additional details are recovered, like their title, augmented and curated set of bibliographic identifiers, year of publication and the list of authors. Also, with the unique internal ID, the list of internal identifiers of manuscript references and each known citation is obtained. Then, the details of each identifier in the reference and citation lists are fetched, in order to classify them by year.
4. After this, there is a consolidation phase for each tool's bibliographic reference, where the gathered citations from all the sources are integrated, so only the unique citations are used for the statistics. The public, bibliographic identifiers of each citation are used for that.

Figure 6. Monitoring tools citations. Example entry: gibbs_motif_sampler

Additionally, a complete set of statistics about the contents of the data warehouse are available through the statistics tabs (Figure 7).

Figure 7. General statistics of tools monitored in OpenEBench.

8.3.2. RESTful API's

Although OpenEBench website gives access to all information stored in the data warehouse in a friendly manner, the platform is designed to provide information in a way that can be integrated in other infrastructures. To this end a series of RESTful API's have been developed (see section 8.7 for a list of the access URLs and specifications). Information from these APIs is obtained in JSON format (see a partial example on Figure 8).

It is relevant to note that information can be obtained for specific versions or specific deployments of the tool (see Figure 8 example). This opens the possibility of performing historical analysis comparing the performance and/or availability of different resources versions.

```
[
  toolID: "biotools:signalp"
  {
    version: "4.1",
    technical:
      {
        avg_response_time: "123",
        up: "Yes",
        ...
      }
    benchmark:
      {
        competition: "https://results.com/result1"
        continuous: "https://openebench.bsc.es/benchmark/toolid=signalp&ver=4.1"
      }
  },
  {
    version: "4.0",
    technical:
      {
        avg_response_time: "345",
        up: "No",
        ...
      }
    benchmark:
      {
        competition: "https://results.com/result1"
        continuous: "https://openebench.bsc.es/benchmark/toolid=signalp&ver=4.0"
      }
  },
  ...
]
```

Figure 8. Partial JSON output from <https://openebench.bsc.es/tool/toolid=signalp>

8.3.3. Widgets

Exporting data from OpenEBench can produce a large amount of data. Representation of such data as part of other infrastructures requires a condensed version that can be easily placed in their web layouts and provide a quick overview of the information available, albeit interested users can still link to the main OpenEBench site.

A number of HTML widgets have been designed²⁰ and implemented. The current widget gallery contains three widgets but it is possible to increase that number in the near future. Widgets are distributed as simple HTML snippets (Figure 9), which made them easily deployable anywhere. Indeed, there are two specific widgets which are used systematically as part of the OpenEBench Tool Card: tools availability (Figure 5) and tools associated publications (Figure 6). A more general widget is depicted in Figure 10 and 11.

```

<html>
<head>
<meta charset="UTF-8" />
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width" />
</head>
<body>
<div data-id="pmut" data-widget-type="widget" data-widget-subtypes="widget" data-widget-size="225" data-widget-tooltip-position="right" class="opeb"></div>
<script type="text/javascript" src="https://openebench.bsc.es/widget/dist/OpEB-widgets.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
  
```

Figure 9. HTML snippet to include OpenEBench tools monitoring widget, for tool pmut. Tool Id is the only parameter that should be adjusted.

In its present form the general widget provides a condensed information on 4 sections of the metrics (Documentation, Support, Buildability, & and License, Table 1). The degree of completion on each aspect is coded as the intensity of colors (Figure 10A). The central icon embeds the tools availability widget (online/offline). The widget is dynamic so additional information is available on hovering the mouse in the appropriate sections (Figure 10B for metrics, and Figure 10C for availability status). OpenEBench widget is already deployed in bio.tools as depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 10. OpenEBench widget prototypes are being already integrated in bio.tools Tools Card.

²⁰ <https://openebench.bsc.es/widget/>

Figure 11. bio.tools card for the PMut tool including OpenEBench widget.

8.4. Coordination with other ELIXIR activities.

As mentioned earlier, OpenEBench aims to become a knowledge hub around the technical monitoring and scientific benchmarking of bioinformatics tools, servers and workflows. In such effort, it is important to be able to integrate data from diverse repositories, especially from the ELIXIR platforms, in order to derive most of the already mentioned quality metrics (Table 1). At the time of writing this report, OpenEBench integrates tools, servers and workflows from four main repositories (Table 3). Importantly, this integration is bidirectional, which will facilitate the later access to all metrics available at OpenEBench by those platforms.

OpenEBench has incorporated the ELIXIR Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (ELIXIR AAI) developed by the ELIXIR Compute Platform as part of the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE WP4 for offering to each user their own working space. This is especially relevant for those participants on the scientific benchmarking activities as they can fully control which data is submitted to each community and how that data is available in OpenEBench e.g. fully private, shared with the community members, shared via a URL, and/or public.

In coordination with the ELIXIR Interoperability platform, OpenEBench now monitors which tools websites implement bioschemas for annotating their tools, servers and/or workflows. When bioschemas tags are detected, OpenEBench makes sure they are compliant accordingly to the implementation promoted by the Interoperability platform. It is being evaluated which additional information can be obtained using bioschemas for broadening the number of quality metrics under evaluation.

In collaboration with the ELIXIR rare-diseases Community, former ELIXIR-EXCELERATE WP8, OpenEBench hosts a community for the analytical pipelines used for the genomics variant

calling. Importantly, OpenEBench will display the persistent URL for the public reference datasets used for carrying on that work²¹. This will facilitate further works in this very active domain.

Going beyond the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE project, OpenEBench is closely working with the H2020 Multiscale Complex Genomics project (<https://www.multiscalegenomics.eu/>) for re-utilizing their virtual research environment (VRE). Adopting and extending MuG VRE will shorten the deployment cycle and benefiting from the *know how* generated in that project. Moreover, it will contribute to move faster to the level 2 and 3 for the scientific benchmarking support levels, as explained in Section 8.6.

Table 3. Summary of the number of tools, servers and workflows imported from available repositories.

Repository	Imported Entries
ELIXIR Tools Registry bio.tools	10,861
bioconda/biocontainers	3,895
Galaxy Shed	1,752
Total Entries (total entries after collapsing redundant ones)	16,508 (15,002)

8.5. Future developments

There are 3 levels to bring in scientific benchmarking data into OpenEBench. First level, currently in production (Step 2, roadmap above), allows mature communities to provide their already generated data via the OpenEBench API. For doing that, communities should follow the publicly available data model and validate their submitted data locally and remotely to ensure data consistency at all levels. Second level (Step 7), currently being tested, provides a virtual research environment (VRE) where communities can deploy workflows for computing scientific metrics given *Metrics Reference Datasets* have been made available. This second level facilitates the support to the scientific communities, especially to the newly assembled ones, as they do not need to have their own infrastructure to conduct benchmarking activities. Thus, communities can focus on defining the relevant challenges they would like to tackle. They only need to provide datasets to participants e.g. **Public Reference Datasets** which can be used for understanding the nature of data at hand, **Input Datasets** which are the one used by participants as starting point to provide their own predictions (**Participant Datasets**); and to OpenEBench

²¹ Laurie S, Fernandez-Callejo M, Marco-Sola S, et al. From wet-lab to variations: Concordance and speed of bioinformatics pipelines for whole genome and whole exome sequencing. *Human Mutation*. 2016;37(12):1263-1271. doi:10.1002/humu.23114.

e.g. **Metrics Reference Dataset** which are the ones used to compute the **Participants Assessment Datasets** at the platform using the metrics workflows uploaded by the community. **Challenge Datasets** are generated when all **Assessment Datasets** are put together before the submission to the OpenEBench database.

Level three (Step 8) will facilitate an unbiased technical and scientific assessment of participants by executing participants workflows under the same environment. For being able to do so, we have started to collaborate with the ELIXIR Compute platform to define mechanisms for software containers e.g. dockers, deployment and execution. Level three will remove the barrier for participants of having to run locally their own predictions in order to take part of any scientific benchmark efforts. Given the scarcity of computational power and available storage, a careful evaluation will be taken about which communities can benefit from level three implementation.

OpenEBench will also make available 4 different modes for visualizing the scientific performance of participants at a given challenge. Level one will show only information to the participants. Level two will show comparison results to all participants taking part of a scientific benchmarking challenge. This will contribute to adjustments and discussion at community level before making data publicly available. Level three will facilitate sharing results via URLs. This mechanism will assist participants and/or communities to share their results to specific people outside their communities e.g. manuscript reviewers, funding bodies, etc. Level four, and the encourage one when a publication is accepted, is making data publicly available to everyone.

8.6. Relevant URLs related to OpenEBench

- **OpenEBench** **Frontend.**
Main OpenEBench website using Angular technologies.
URL: <https://openebench.bsc.es>
Repository: <https://github.com/inab/OpenEBenchFrontend>
- **OpenEBench** **Widgets.**
Repository for the OpenEBench widgets gallery, which facilitate accessing and consuming data in other platforms.
URL: <https://openebench.bsc.es/widget>
Repository: <https://github.com/inab/OpenEBench-widgets>
- **Scientific Benchmarking** **API.**
RESTful API to obtain data from scientific benchmarking events registered at OpenEBench.

API: <https://openebench.bsc.es/api/scientific>
Repository - Data Model: <https://github.com/inab/benchmarking-data-model>
Repository - API: <https://github.com/inab/OpenEBenchAPI>

- **ELIXIBILITAS. The OpenEBench Tools Monitoring platform.**
ELIXIBILITAS is the codename for the tools monitoring platform at OpenEBench. This project is in JAVA and strictly adherent to the [JEE8](#) specification. The ELIXIBILITAS platform is developed and deployed on [WildFly 10.1](#) server, but should run on other servers i.e. [Apache Tomcat](#).

API: <https://openebench.bsc.es/monitor/tool/>

Open API 3.0 specification: <https://openebench.bsc.es/monitor/openapi.json>

Repository: <https://github.com/inab/elixibilitas>

Ontology: <https://openebench.bsc.es/monitor/tools.owl>

Tool JSON Schema: <https://openebench.bsc.es/monitor/tool/tool.json>

Metrics JSON Schema: <https://openebench.bsc.es/monitor/metrics/metrics.json>

- **Publications Data Enrichers.**
Repository containing the mechanisms for gathering data from different publications archives and the posterior data integration.

Repository: <https://github.com/inab/opeb-enrichers/tree/master/pubEnricher>